

DESERT FOOD FUTURES

Exploring the Value of Situated Methods in Design Education

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ABSTRACT

What can be used for cooking in desert environments, and how can the intersection of environmental and cultural thinking with digital technologies create opportunities for innovative modes of food preparation? The paper fits the session "Design & Build: Form Follows Availability," emphasizing the importance of aligning design solutions with locally sourced materials and renewable energy to reduce dependence on external resources, while integrating regional cultural traditions to optimize the utility of these materials, particularly in harsh environments. This approach contributes to a broader understanding of how design in harsh climates can be more sustainable, reduce its carbon footprint, and promote cultural continuity. To illustrate this, the paper critically examines the work developed during an undergraduate design course, where students explored the relationship between product design and a specific environmental and cultural context in the UAE. The outcome was a series of innovative portable solar-powered cooking systems, tools, and food recipes, using solar energy, local materials, traditional cultural methods, and digital technologies. The paper introduces a fresh agenda emphasizing how situated methods and digital technologies contribute to the development of innovative design processes that are more sustainable and stimulate cultural preservation.

1. INTRODUCTION

The paper relates to the main theme of decarbonization by examining how design can minimize environmental impact through the use of solar energy and locally sourced materials, which inherently reduce reliance on external resources, while also incorporating regional cultural traditions to maximize the utility of local resources (Sardana et al., 2024). By employing methods that encourage the use of renewable energy, local resources, and traditional cooking techniques, the paper contributes to a broader understanding of how design in harsh climates can be more sustainable and have a reduced carbon footprint.

To illustrate this, the paper presents a second-year undergraduate workshop course titled "Materials in Human Experiences." The course was designed as a Product Design module at the Dubai Institute of Design and Innovation (DIDI) in Dubai, UAE to provide students with knowledge about the relationship between materials, production processes, and the ecological and cultural contexts in which they exist, while also equipping them with the tools to engage with the world beyond workshop and studio settings. Thus, a transdisciplinary approach was adopted to ground students' design work in situated environmental, sociocultural, and technological factors.

Students' learning occurred through the integration of knowledge from human-centered design to more-than-human theory, achieved through direct engagement in the field and at the DIDI's Fab Lab. The chosen site was Al Qudra, a sand desert located approximately 30 km from the center of Dubai. This area provided a unique opportunity to explore how locally available resources could inspire students to develop innovative and more sustainable solutions. It also offered insight into how Bedouin communities have adapted to the harsh environmental conditions—characterized by extreme temperatures, limited water sources, scarce vegetation, and few species of animals—by developing practices that maximize the utility of available resources. The combination of fieldwork and Fab Lab activities facilitated the integration of opportunities presented by both the environmental conditions and cultural traditions, while incorporating situated design methods (Simonsen et al., 2014) and digital technologies (Soomro et al., 2021), leading to the development of innovative cooking solutions tailored to the desert environment.

The course required students to design portable solar-powered cooking systems, tools, and food recipes. Each team aligned its project with a primary available ecological resource—such as sand, solar energy, local plants, or animals—while integrating cultural traditions and

new technologies. In doing so, students had to examine how processes of inhabiting and understanding specific environmental settings influenced the conceptualization and development of products, as well as their comprehension of these relationships.

The paper explores how design can address ecological and social challenges, focusing on environmental sustainability and cultural preservation by integrating this knowledge with digital technologies.

2. ABOUT SITUATEDNESS

The effects of technological and environmental changes are pushing designers to work on complicated socio-technical systems (Forlano, 2017), which requires them to learn about methodological approaches that extend beyond disciplinary boundaries. This embodied approach acknowledges that the multiple relations formed when things are lived through (or inhabited) produce different meanings. Donna Haraway refers to the result of these meaning-making processes as “situated knowledges” (Haraway, 1988). By refusing to distance the knowing subject from what one seeks to know, such knowledges emerge from specific pathways and “partial perspectives” (Haraway, 1988). Following Haraway, Simonsen (2014) claims that “all design is situated,” meaning that it is based on processes that develop within specific social contexts and are carried out from an “embedded” position (Simonsen et al., 2014, p. 6).

Situated knowledges provide a relational and context-specific understanding of the human experience rather than aiming at generalizing it to draw universal assumptions. As such, they can be complex and even contradictory, but they offer the advantage of opening to in-depth analysis of lived experiences. Boud and Walker (1998) argued that ‘context’ represents “the single most important influence on learning and reflection” (Boud & Walker, 1998), recognizing at the same time its underdeveloped dimension in the production and discussion of design.

Practitioners of situated pedagogy and Situated Learning (Jean & Wenger, 1991) draw on traditions of experiential education to support the value of direct experience within the design process. Building on John Dewey’s (1966) work, ‘experience’ is interpreted as the process of acting upon our surroundings and undergoing the consequences of our actions in return (Dewey, 1966). Transposed into educational settings, learning through experiences assumes that when students are involved in design projects in specific environmental contexts, they experiment with the settings of such contexts to find out what they are and how they work (Frandsen & Pfeiffer Peterson, 2014).

As suggested by Gaver (2022), approaching design research from a situated, practice-based perspective does not come without concerns. This very mode of positioning designers, for instance, seems to contradict more established traditions about research as a systematic, positivist, inquiry-driven process (Gaver et al., 2022). This similarly applies to the context of design education, where students are often trained to approach design from a problem-solving perspective in a studio or workshop environment, thus physically distancing students from the problems they are asked to 'solve'. This mode of learning arguably prevents students' engagement with complexity as it fails to expose them to lateral, critical thinking. The question of what implications a situated approach to design might have on design students remains largely underexplored.

2.1. METHODOLOGY

The workshop course consisted of 3 hours per week, with students divided into groups of 3 to 6 participants. The methodology involved a dynamic exchange of information using various methods and research techniques, allowing students to develop a personal mode of inquiry toward the environment. The course was structured into three interconnected phases: fieldwork explorations, data visualization, and prototyping.

2.1.1. SITUATED DESIGN IN UNDERGRADUATE EDUCATION

The brief provided to the class, along with the designated site, outlined the types of designs students were expected to develop: portable solar-powered devices for cooking in the desert, tools for preparing or eating food, and new recipes using local ingredients informed by traditional methods. The expected outcomes were intentionally kept open to avoid prescribing specific directions for the design work.

2.1.2. FIELDWORK: OBSERVING AND UNDERSTANDING

Fieldwork provides valuable ethnographic engagement through hands-on experiences, enabling researchers to observe and develop a personal understanding of a situation. In the beginning of the course, students visited the Al Qudra desert individually, with a three-hour main visit guided by professors. As this was the students' first experience with ethnographic research at a site far from the DIDI's campus, they were divided into groups and given suggestions on tactics for collecting observational evidence, such as monitoring protocols to measure heat and humidity, physical sampling of on-site materials, audio-visual recordings (photos and sound), annotated diaries, sketches, and interactions with local dwellers.

2.1.3. DATA VISUALISATION: MAPPING AS WORLD SENSE-MAKING

The objective of using mapping as a research tool was to guide students in engaging with site-specific research from a visual perspective. As a qualitative tool, mapping can help "evoke the lived experience of social, cultural, and political issues related to place" (Powell, 2010). After the fieldwork, each group was asked to deliver a data visualization that represented the relationships between place, lived experience, and community within the studied desert area.

2.1.4. PROTOTYPING: MAKING AS SYNTHETISING KNOWLEDGE

During the prototyping phase, each group progressed from sketches to technical drawings and three-dimensional models. Students tested low-fidelity prototypes of various sizes and materials, such as cardboard, blue foam, and MDF, before transitioning to more durable materials through an iterative process of prototyping and refining ideas (Goudswaard et al., 2023). These quick prototypes helped students better understand the project's complexity and test the functionality of their concepts on-site. Subsequently, students refined their prototypes, considering factors such as ergonomics, sustainability, and cultural relevance to create the final high-fidelity prototype.

The integration of digital tools (e.g., Rhino, SolidWorks) (Ikubanni et al., 2022) and digital fabrication processes (e.g., laser cutting, 3D printing, CNC machines) (Soomro et al., 2021), enabled the detailed and precise production of both low- and high-fidelity prototypes (King, 2019).

2.1.5. REPORTS AND EVALUATION METHODOLOGY

The paper follows a double reflective process involving professors and students. Each group submitted an initial report on the design process, including a reflexive essay. The professors reviewed and edited these reports, providing feedback. Students then revised their texts, adding missing or meaningful parts. The final text incorporated various viewpoints and provided multiple layers of analysis: professors assessed the students' understanding of the design process, while students reflected on the professors' perspectives and feedback.

3. RESULTS

3.1. TRAP N COOK

The results of this research are presented through four distinct group projects. In the first project, students analyzed the nutrient groups required for a balanced diet and categorized local plants and animals accordingly (Figure 1). The cooking system was designed to trap animals and combine them with desert plants to meet human nutritional needs.

Figure 1: Data visualization illustrating the interaction of animals on-site and their nutrient percentages

Different trap designs were tested (Figure 2). The first two used shoe boxes with various baits, covered with cling film and a hole on top to allow ants, insects, and beetles to enter while preventing their escape. The third design used a water bottle, cut to create a funnel shape that directed ants and beetles into the bottle, attracted by maple syrup.

Figure 2: Trap 01: white box, trap 02: dark blue box, and trap 03: cut bottle

The next phase involved selecting the most efficient trap and integrating it with a grilling system, enabling the animals to be captured and cooked on-site. A prototype was built using cardboard and foam (Figure 3). It was later refined into a metal box with a reflective lid designed to enhance the heating process, similar to the functioning of an oven (Figures 4, 5).

Figure 3: Prototype of the cooking device made from cardboard and foam

Figure 4:
Final prototype of the cooking device

Figure 5:
Final prototype of the cooking device, featuring colored animals to illustrate its working mechanisms

3.2. VEGGIE COOKING

The second project focused on a plant-based approach, using edible desert flora. Students identified key plants on-site, such as the Ghaf tree, Toothbrush tree, and Saltbush shrub (Figure 6), which hold cultural and medicinal value in the UAE, and adapted traditional Emirati recipes to incorporate these plants into new dishes.

Figure 6:
Diagram of the main plants found on-site

The project was inspired by a traditional method of heating stones to boil water. Students used a Fresnel lens to direct sunlight into a metal container with a concentrator to heat the stones placed inside. Once the stones were heated, they used them to boil water and cook local ingredients and leaves for soups and salads (Figure 7).

Figure 7:
Reference image of traditional cooking with stones and the food recipes proposed by the students

Cardboard prototypes were created to test different proposals (Figure 8). The final design featured a hexagonal-patterned steel body with four compartments for heating stones. The Fresnel lens was mounted on a swing arm, allowing precise adjustment to focus sunlight on the stones. To facilitate the use of various types of leaves, a 3D-printed leaf grinder made with wood-based filament was created (Figure 9).

Figure 8:
Cardboard prototypes of the cooking device and the leaf grinder

Figure 9:
Final prototypes of the cooking device and the leaf grinder

3.3. COOKING WITH SAND

The third project drew inspiration from Bedouin cooking traditions, which use desert sand as a heat source. Students investigated how sand color influences temperature, mapping variations across the desert to identify optimal conditions for cooking food directly in the sand (Figures 10, 11).

THE AFFECT OF TEMPERATURE (IN °) ON THE SAND COLOR AT DIFFERENT SURFACES

Figure 10: Diagram illustrating that 80% of the UAE consists of desert land and highlighting variations in sand colors, and data visualization showing the relationship between sand color and temperature

Figure 11: Data visualization showing the temperature variations of the atmosphere at different times of the day

Students developed a series of recipes inspired by traditional Bedouin dishes (Figure 12) and created a device that could be easily assembled and disassembled, making it suitable for use in the desert. Cardboard, MDF and clay prototypes were created to test different proposals (Figures 13,14). The final device featured a Fresnel lens to concentrate sunlight onto a central cooking pot filled with sand, which then distributed heat to smaller clay pots containing the food (Figures 15, 16).

Figure 12: Diagram comparing traditional food cooking times and temperatures, alongside the food recipes proposed by the students

Figure 13:
Prototypes made from cardboard, clay, and paper

Figure 14:
Prototypes of various materials and a backpack for transporting the cooking device

Figure 15:
Final prototype disassembled and assembled

Figure 16:
Final prototype showing the clay pots for food preparation

3.4. RIMAL

Rimal in Arabic refers to the sandy terrain in desert regions. This fourth project challenged the idea that cooking must always result in edible outcomes. It reimagined sand, combined with on-site plants (Figure 17) and other elements, as a potential "ingredient," offering sustainable alternatives to plastic dishes by emphasizing local resources and bio-entities.

Initial Desert Exploration

AL QUDRA DESERT IN DUBAI, UAE 3:40 PM 21ST SEPTEMBER

Figure 17: Diagram of key plants found on-site that could be used as ingredients alongside sand

The project process began with hypotheses and iterative testing, adjusting ingredients to assess functional and aesthetic qualities. Cornstarch, aloe and egg whites were tested for material resistance, while turmeric, sumac, charcoal and Ghaf tree leaves were explored as natural colorants. The final recipe combined sand, okra, and lime in a 40:50:20 ratio, resulting in a moldable paste for crafting cutlery and plates that could be "baked" over an open fire on-site.

Students focused on local materials, avoiding additives like colorants. To explore the aesthetic variations of sand, however, they collected samples not only on-site but also from multiple locations across the UAE, recording GPS coordinates. These samples revealed unique color tones, reflecting the geographical identity of each artifact (Figure 18).

Figure 18: Samples of sand with various colors and textures

The kit developed for the project included laser-cut wooden stencils designed to be wrapped around wooden sticks. The stencils were filled with the sand mixture and heated over a fire, where the lime and okra served as natural binders, solidifying the material. Additionally, the kit also included a portable metal oven to bake the tools.

The outcome was a collection of molded artifacts functioning as cutlery and plates. This work exemplifies a situated approach to materiality and sustainability, integrating both the aesthetic and functional properties of sand into a cohesive design narrative (Figures 19, 20, 21,22).

Figure 19:
**Molded artifacts, stencils
and prototype of the oven**

Figure 20:
Molded artifacts and stencils

Figure 21:
Molded artifacts and stencils

Figure 22:
Exhibition during the Design Week with all the final prototypes

4. CRITICAL DISCUSSION

The course presented in this paper encouraged students to understand and engage with complex concepts, such as "situated knowledge" (Haraway, 1988) and "experience" (Dewey, 1966). This section highlights the insights gathered and discusses the course's limitations as potential starting points for future work.

Despite a transdisciplinary effort, students often felt unprepared to conduct ethnographic studies in the field. (1) One difficulty was separating their general knowledge of the 'desert' from the subjective, in-situ experience of a specific desert patch in a precise geographical area. This challenge sometimes led to biased explorations and unoriginal content. (2) Another challenge was distinguishing field research- as an activity aimed at observing and gathering information - from design - intended as a generative future-oriented activity. This led students to work influenced by the constraints of hypothetical designs and production processes. To address this, delaying the reveal of the course's design goal until after the fieldwork phase could help students focus on understanding the context before seeking solutions. (3) Students struggled with ethnographies on non-human entities; enhancements could include developing tools to monitor other species.

A noteworthy point of discussion is the evolving role of the Fab lab, as encouraging students to look beyond its tools led to new insights into 'transformation. This applied to both 'materials' and 'observations' as students processed their fieldwork in stages: ethnographic, analytical, designerly, and finally, mechanical. This progression redefined the lab as a versatile space, incorporating multiple sites, processes, and connections. Transformation, in this context, extends beyond the lab and its machinery, involving interactions with external elements like plants, sand, heat, and other environmental agents. Thus, the FabLab can be envisioned as an extended, diffused space where fabrication occurs in various locations and through different means.

5. CONCLUSION

The paper highlights the importance of designing-with the environment rather than for it. It intends to stimulate reflections on environmental and cultural thinking, as well as the value of process-oriented, experience-based, and situated learning in design education, while also offering a critique of its current issues and directions. The results suggest that product design benefits from situated methods and digital technologies, requiring students to understand the context and how these technologies can support the design and fabrication process. Students noted that this experience influenced their project framing, helping them grasp the ecosystem's peculiarities and lay the foundations for their final projects. However, some students found the ethnographic methods proposed for the course to be complex. Additional concerns included the environmental conditions in which the fieldwork activities took place, that is, some of the hottest days of Dubai's summer months.

Finally, although students successfully connected environmental settings with specific materials and digital technologies in their projects, the designs were somewhat disconnected from the site's possibilities. Incorporating the concept of a 'displaced laboratory' could extend design and fabrication beyond the lab's walls, recognizing environmental processes as transformative agents. Future studies could explore how to implement these transitions, taking into account the age and preparation of undergraduate design students. It could also include additional quantitative data on resource and energy savings, or comparisons with traditional cooking methods, which could emphasize the environmental advantages of these designs.

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